

Automotive-Low-cost Greenhouse Structure as an adaptable solution for smart urban farming; pathway for sustainable agriculture

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Abstract

Greenhouses are controlled environments designed to enhance crop quality and yield while reducing the risks associated with climate variability, pests, and diseases. Despite their proven benefits, greenhouse adoption in Sri Lanka and other developing countries remains limited due to high initial costs, lack of technical knowledge, and limited awareness of modern agricultural technologies. This study aims to bridge that gap by designing, constructing, and automating a low-cost, small-scale greenhouse system suitable for urban and semi-urban households with restricted space and resources. The project integrates solar energy, drip irrigation, and IoT-based environmental monitoring to create a sustainable modern greenhouse system. A lightweight reinforced frame covered with UV-resistant polyethylene was used to protect crops from pests and environmental stress. Bell peppers were chosen as the test crop due to their moderate climate needs and economic value. An Arduino Uno controlled irrigation, and monitored soil moisture, soil temperature, and humidity, with real-time data shown on an LCD display. When soil moisture dropped below the set threshold, a buzzer-activated drip irrigation system automatically operated. Solar panels powered LED grow lights and a ventilation fan, ensuring optimal growing conditions with minimal human intervention. The greenhouse was implemented in the Kandy District in Sri Lanka's Central Province, where the tropical highland climate (20°C–28°C, 2,000–3,000 mm annual rainfall) supports bell pepper cultivation. However, greenhouse-grown bell peppers may not perform well in regions with high humidity or temperatures above 30°C, hence local climate suitability must be considered before adoption. The system improved water-use efficiency, reduced reliance on chemical fertilizers, and produced healthier organic crops. It also minimized manual labor, saving time and energy.

Keywords: *Low-Cost, Greenhouse, Automation, IoT (Internet of Things), Solar Energy, Sustainable Agriculture*